
195. Imaging of the Galaxy bar

I DISCUSSED SOME aspects of our Galaxy's central bar in essay 112: how bars in general are believed to originate, the evidence for a bar in our own Galaxy, and inferences being made from kinematic studies with Gaia.

These included estimates of the bar's length, its 'pattern speed', why it affects motions in the solar neighbourhood via resonances, and evidence that the bar is slowing down, over cosmological time scales, due to dynamical friction dominated by the dark matter halo.

Here, I will say more about the attempts (and difficulties) of elucidating its morphology, and include a surprising demonstration of Gaia's ability to image it.

OCCUPYING OUR Galaxy's inner few kpc is a dense concentration of mostly old stars in a roughly spheroidal 'bulge'. Departures from circularity were inferred from 21-cm H I observations by de Vaucouleurs (1964), and its triaxial structure first discerned more directly from 24 μm observations (Blitz & Spergel, 1991), and near-infrared COBE data (Weiland et al., 1994; Dwek et al., 1995; Freudenreich, 1998).

Many subsequent efforts have been made to discern its detailed structure, as a step to understanding its origin. Work focused on the bar's morphology includes use of the colour-magnitude diagram of red clump stars from OGLE (Stanek et al., 1994; Rattenbury et al., 2007); and using infrared star counts from 2MASS, DENIS, ISO, GLIMPSE, UKIDSS, and VVV (López-Corredoira et al., 2001; Picaud & Robin, 2004; Babusiaux & Gilmore, 2005; Benjamin et al., 2005; Cabrera-Lavers et al., 2008; Wegg et al., 2015; Simion et al., 2017).

The detailed morphology still remains unclear, e.g. whether it is peanut-shaped, or whether there are additional components. Estimates still vary widely concerning its axis ratio, its half-length (1–5 kpc), and its orientation with respect to the Galactic centre (10–45°).

Its stellar population content, and its formation and evolutionary history, also remain poorly constrained. Two or more overlapping populations might exist, complicating estimates of its shape and orientation (e.g. Martínez-Valpuesta & Gerhard, 2011).

IN ONE SPECIFIC model, which I will refer to later, Robin et al. (2012) made a two-component fit to star counts, colour-magnitude diagrams, and metallicities. Their principal component was a triaxial ellipsoid with scale lengths 1.46/0.49/0.39 kpc, at an orientation of 13°.

IN THEIR REVIEW, Bland-Hawthorn & Gerhard (2016) emphasised the difficulties in separating the bar and bulge, the inner disk and inner halo, and the possibility of a 'super-thin' contribution. They gave best estimates as: *stellar* mass ($7 \pm 1 \times 10^9 M_\odot$), half-length (5.0 ± 0.2 kpc), scale height (180 pc), orientation (28–33°), and an age of 6–7 Gyr (see also Sormani et al., 2022).

As they stated at the time, its pattern speed ($43 \pm 9 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$) and corresponding corotation radius (4.5–7 kpc), derived mainly from numerical and hydrodynamical simulations, also remain poorly determined.

MUCH NEW INSIGHT has come from recent kinematic measurements and associated modelling using the Gaia data. I will give just a brief summary of some of the findings I mentioned in essay 112.

From Gaia DR2 and VVV-VIRAC, Sanders et al. (2019) and Clarke et al. (2019) showed that differential rotation between the double peaks of the magnitude distribution of red clump giants confirms the X-shaped nature of the bar-bulge identified by Wegg & Gerhard (2013), and consistent with a pattern speed of $37.5 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$.

Bovy et al. (2019) used APOGEE DR16 with Gaia DR2, while Leung et al. (2023) updated the analysis using APOGEE DR17 with Gaia EDR3, to identify the minimum in rotational velocity, and the quadrupole signature in radial velocity, expected for stars orbiting in a bar. They estimated a pattern speed of $40.1 \pm 1.8 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ kpc}^{-1}$.

Other Gaia-based studies have given other estimates of the bar length and pattern speed (Clarke & Gerhard, 2022; Drimmel et al., 2023; Lucey et al., 2023). A remarkable if preliminary conclusion, based on models of resonance sweeping, is that the bar is decelerating, an effect attributable to dynamical friction of a dark matter halo (Chiba et al., 2021; Chiba & Schönrich, 2021).

THE LEFT FIGURE ABOVE, from Shen & Zheng (2020), is an artist impression of the Milky Way viewed face-on (top), with the infrared COBE–DIRBE image showing the box-like bar (bottom). The right figure shows the bar and bulge projections derived from near-infrared star counts by Wegg et al. (2015).

More details of the bulge–bar structure, interpretation of the X-shaped feature, and of associated dynamical models, are given by Shen & Zheng (2020).

And as summarised in their review of the chemo-dynamical history of the bulge, Barbuy et al. (2018) noted that ‘*Despite impressive progress, we do not yet have a successful fully self-consistent chemo-dynamical bulge model in the cosmological framework, and we will also need a more extensive chrono-chemical-kinematic 3D map of stars to better constrain such models*’.

THINGS HAVE progressed with Gaia since then, but here I will look only at one study which has essentially been able to image the bulge, at least more directly than reconstructions based on number counts.

Anders et al. (2019) used the *StarHorse* code on a combination of Pan–STARRS1, 2MASS, and ALLWISE photometry with Gaia DR2 parallaxes to derive stellar parameters, distances, and extinctions for 137 million stars with $G \leq 18$ mag. Resulting median precisions were 5% in distance, 0.20 mag in V -band extinction, and 245 K in T_{eff} for $G \leq 14$, degrading at fainter magnitudes.

StarHorse (Santiago et al., 2016; Queiroz et al., 2018) finds the (Bayesian) posterior probability over a grid of stellar evolutionary models, distances, and extinctions, given a set of observations plus a number of priors: here, the initial mass function, density laws for the thin disk, thick disk, bulge, and halo, as well as broad metallicity and age priors for each component.

The upper figure opposite shows the face-on projection of the stellar density distribution of their final sample in Galactic XY coordinates. The lack of stars towards the inner Galaxy is attributed to identified effects of the high dust extinction and the adopted quality criteria.

Especially noteworthy is the presence of a stellar overdensity coinciding with the expected position of the Galactic bar, inclined by about 40° with respect to the solar azimuth, and with a semi-major axis of ~ 4 kpc.

The presence of the bar in the Gaia DR2 data is even more prominent when focusing only on the red clump stars (lower figure). Interestingly, its revealed shape and inclination are significantly different from their adopted prior, which was given by the Galactic bulge–bar model derived by Robin et al. (2012), and noted above. They also identified a kinematic imprint of the coherent motion of the Galactic bar in the proper motions.

That Gaia is probing stellar populations in the Galactic bulge and beyond is, at first sight, surprising. They reason that their distance estimates are not more *precise* than those prescribed by, e.g., Bailer-Jones et al. (2018), using which the bar is barely evident. However, at large distances, their values (they argue) are more *accurate*, due to the use of more informative Galactic priors.

Further discussion of the velocities and chemo-dynamical implications, based on Gaia EDR3, were reported by Queiroz et al. (2021), who also interpreted their results in the context of numerical simulations of barred galaxies (e.g. Debattista et al., 2017; Bovy et al., 2019; Carrillo et al., 2019; Fragkoudi et al., 2020).

